

Annex B3 – Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter*

Annex to: EUSR on AMR in zoonotic and indicator bacteria from humans, animals and food 2023/2024

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Trends in resistance to Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin and Tetracycline in *C. coli* from fattening pigs, 2014-2024

Resistance to: Ciprofloxacin (CIP) Erythromycin (ERY) Tetracycline (TET)

Figure 1 - Trends in ciprofloxacin (CIP), erythromycin (ERY) and tetracycline (TET) resistance in *Campylobacter coli* from fattening pigs, 2014–2024.

(A)

(B)

Figure 2 - Trends in ciprofloxacin (CIP), erythromycin (ERY) and tetracycline (TET) resistance in A) *Campylobacter jejuni* and B) *C. coli* from calves, 2014–2024

(A)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. jejuni* from broilers and turkeys, 2024

(B)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. coli* from broilers and turkeys, 2024

(C)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. jejuni* from pigs and cattle (< 1 year of age), 2023

(D)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. coli* from pigs and cattle (< 1 year of age), 2023

Figure 3 - Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in (A) *C. jejuni* from broilers and fattening turkeys, (B) *C. coli* from broilers and fattening turkeys, (C) *C. jejuni* from fattening pigs and calves, (D) *C. coli* from fattening pigs and calves, in reporting MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2023 and 2024

Figure 4 Prevalence of resistance to ciprofloxacin (A), erythromycin (B), tetracycline (C) and related 95% confidence intervals in *Campylobacter jejuni* from broilers, per reporting country, 2024

Figure 5 Prevalence of resistance to ciprofloxacin (A), erythromycin (B), tetracycline (C) and related 95% confidence intervals in *Campylobacter jejuni* from fattening turkeys, per reporting country, 2024

Figure 6 Prevalence of resistance to ciprofloxacin (A), erythromycin (B), tetracycline (C) and related 95% confidence intervals in *Campylobacter coli* from broilers, per reporting country, 2024.

Figure 7 Prevalence of resistance to ciprofloxacin (A), erythromycin (B), tetracycline (C) and related 95% confidence intervals in *Campylobacter coli* from fattening turkeys, per reporting country, 2024.